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**TRENDS OF SMOKING AMONG MEDICAL
STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT:

Smoking is a practice in which a substance is burned, and the resulting smoke is breathed in to be tasted and absorbed into the bloodstream. Most commonly, the substance used is the dried leaves of the tobacco plant, which have been rolled into a small square of rice paper to create a small, round cylinder called a "cigarette". This cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students of different classes of different medical colleges. Brief demographic data i.e. name, age, gender, smoking habits, reasons of smoking was recorded on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 80 medical students were included in this study. There were 40 (50%) male students and 40 (50%) female students. The mean age of the students was 22.45±1.67 years. A total of 23 medical students including 19 males and 4 females told that they do smoking on regular or occasional pattern. The main reasons of smoking were stress, educational pressure or company of friends.

Keywords: Smoking

INTRODUCTION:

Smoking is a practice in which a substance is burned, and the resulting smoke is breathed in to be tasted and absorbed into the bloodstream. Most commonly, the substance used is the dried leaves of the tobacco plant, which have been rolled into a small square of rice paper to create a small, round cylinder called a "cigarette". Smoking is primarily practised as a route of administration for recreational drug use because the combustion of the dried plant leaves vaporizes and delivers active substances into the lungs where they are rapidly absorbed into the bloodstream and reach bodily tissue. In the case of cigarette smoking these substances are contained in a mixture of aerosol particles and gases and include the pharmacologically active alkaloid nicotine; the vaporization creates heated aerosol and gas into a form that allows inhalation and deep penetration into the lungs where absorption into the bloodstream of

the active substances occurs. In some cultures, smoking is also carried out as a part of various rituals, where participants use it to help induce trance-like states that, they believe, can lead them to spiritual enlightenment.

Smoking is one of the most common forms of recreational drug use. Tobacco smoking is the most popular form, being practised by over one billion people globally, of whom the majority are in the developing countries. Less common drugs for smoking include cannabis and opium. Some of the substances are classified as hard narcotics, like heroin, but the use of these is very limited as they are usually not commercially available. Smoking can be dated to as early as 5000 BCE, and has been recorded in many different cultures across the world. Early smoking evolved in association with religious ceremonies; as offerings to deities, in cleansing rituals or to allow shamans and priests to alter their minds for

purposes of divination or spiritual enlightenment. After the European exploration and conquest of the Americas, the practice of smoking tobacco quickly spread to the rest of the world. In regions like India and Sub-Saharan Africa, it merged with existing practices of smoking (mostly of cannabis). In Europe, it introduced a new type of social activity and a form of drug intake which previously had been unknown.

Material of Methods:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students of different classes of different medical colleges. Brief demographic data i.e. name, age, gender, smoking habits, reasons of smoking was recorded on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 23.0. The qualitative variables were presented as numbers and frequencies. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

A total of 80 medical students were included in this study. There were 40 (50%) male students and 40 (50%) female students.

The mean age of the students was 22.45 ± 1.67 years. A total of 23 medical students including 19 males and 4 females told that they do smoking on regular or occasional pattern. The main reasons of smoking were stress, educational pressure or company of friends.

DISCUSSION:

Smoking is one of the leading causes of preventable death globally and is the cause of 15% of all deaths. In the United States about 500,000 deaths per year are attributed to smoking-related diseases and a recent study estimated that as much as 1/3 of China's male population will have significantly shortened life-spans due to smoking. Male and female smokers lose an average of 13.2 and 14.5 years of life, respectively. At least half of all lifelong smokers die

earlier as a result of smoking. The risk of dying from lung cancer before age 85 is 22.1% for a male smoker and 11.9% for a female current smoker, in the absence of competing causes of death. The corresponding estimates for lifelong nonsmokers are a 1.1% probability of dying from lung cancer before age 85 for a man of European descent, and a 0.8% probability for a woman. Smoking just one cigarette a day results in a risk of coronary heart disease that is halfway between that of a heavy smoker and a non-smoker. The non-linear dose-response relationship may be explained by smoking's effect on platelet aggregation.

Among the diseases that can be caused by smoking are vascular stenosis, lung cancer, heart attacks and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Smoking during pregnancy may cause ADHD to a fetus.

Smoking is a risk factor strongly associated with periodontitis and tooth loss. The effects of smoking on

periodontal tissues depend on the number of cigarettes smoked daily and the duration of the habit . A study showed that smokers had 2.7 times and former smokers 2.3 times greater probabilities to have established periodontal disease than non-smokers, independent of age, sex and plaque index, however, the effect of tobacco on periodontal tissues seems to be more pronounced in men than in women. Studies have found that smokers had greater odds for more severe dental bone loss compared to non-smokers , also, people who smoke and drink alcohol heavily have much higher risk of developing oral cancer (mouth and lip) compared with people who do neither. Smoking can also cause melanosis in the mouth.

Many governments are trying to deter people from smoking with anti-smoking campaigns in mass media stressing the harmful long-term effects of smoking. Passive smoking, or secondhand smoking, which affects people in the immediate

vicinity of smokers, is a major reason for the enforcement of smoking bans (4-6).

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